

Logistics Lessons Learned

A brief commentary on how the workshop was run, how the program committee was managed, how asynchronous contribution was encouraged, and similar ideas. A bulleted format is chosen to keep the ideas and lessons learned easy to read.

Introduction

- Members of the program committee are in different time zones across the US -> need fewer PC meetings and more chances to work asynchronously
- Hybrid meeting -> more technology needed, but also need links between the technologies to be intuitive and obvious.
- Code of conduct issues can come from anyone, including those on a committee. Make sure to have a code of conduct from the beginning and enforce it, including removing a person from a committee if needed.

Methods for asynchronous contributions from EC and PC

- Google survey forms
 - PC opinion on the importance of the software categories and lifecycle stages. This helped guide decisions on assigning moderators to the lightning and discussion sessions.
 - Abstract results: PC rejection recommendations and suggestions for oral presentations.
 - PC ideas for inspirational speakers.
- Spreadsheets
 - Abstracts results: Removed names, emails, institutions, and other details from the abstract information collected via the registration form to reduce bias in PC abstract feedback.
 - **Lesson learned:** would have been less work for PC members if 1-2 people were assigned to the software categories assigned to a given session instead of every PC members having to read through the entire set of abstracts. Some initial review was needed to remove duplicates, proposed discussion topics, and fake entries and collect a missing title or two.
 - Abstract assignments: Abstract sorting leads were able to asynchronously order the lightning talks in each session.
 - **Lesson learned:** keep abstracts for different software categories in different sheets in the spreadsheet. Only allow editing access for abstract sorting leads.
 - Workshop report: PC members were able to classify the numerous takeaways from the workshop into four categories in a spreadsheet without numerous meetings.

- Various spreadsheets linked from google surveys allowed for more detailed analyses of the survey results.
- Docs
 - Group effort to take notes and make comments during PC meetings gave PC members more hesitant to verbally contribute to still make valuable comments and contributions during meetings. This also allowed some problematic contributions, but overall well worth enabling the capability.
 - Similar approach to the EC meetings also had positive effects on our progress.
 - **Lesson learned:** keep longer pieces of text in a separate document from the meeting notes for easier navigation. Bookmark links are not enough and can be confusing.
- Recordings
 - All PC meetings were recorded and linked from the PC notes Google doc to allow PC members that could not attend that specific meeting to hear the conversation and instructions.
 - The training session for the session moderators was also recorded for the selected moderators to be able to complete the training and assigned tasks asynchronously, even if they could not attend the training meeting.
 - **Lesson learned:** Recordings of how to use the various technologies would have also been useful for the workshop attendees. This could have been played during the first logistics instructions session during the workshop for increased awareness.
- General
 - Emails were sent a few days before each contribution deadline to remind PC members of the requested contribution. Some of these emails were sent only to PC members from whom the contribution requested was not yet received to minimize spam.
 - **Lesson learned:** Creating pathways for PC members to contribute via google survey forms, spreadsheets, and similar technologies allowed for fewer meetings with the PC while keeping the possible contribution level high.
 - Shared the entire workshop working directory with all members of EC to encourage teamwork in progress and behavior monitoring and in contribution.
 - **Lesson Learned:** Include the day number in the name of the files to make it easier to determine which 2E session the notes doc corresponds to (e.g. Day 1 2E session vs Day 2 2E session).

Technologies and approaches for a hybrid meeting

- Google suite methods
 - Google docs for collaborative note taking.
 - Not all moderators signed into the google doc or Miro board. Don't know who to contact for additional context on the takeaways from that session.

- Google slides to collect takeaways from breakout sessions in the same place as the links to the notes and Miro boards for those breakout sessions (given in the Report Back session on Day 1). This approach also enabled discussion moderators to more easily upload and present pictures of the physical notes (e.g. instead of a Miro board) with the ideas and thoughts from the participants in the sessions. Create a google doc for notes to document any additional discussion after the takeaways are presented from each breakout session.
- Alternative approach tested was collecting these takeaways from breakout discussion sessions into a Google doc ('Report Back'). This approach made the short presentations from each session moderator less appealing and the related links more difficult to navigate to.
- Less than 3-5% of takeaways were not properly copied into the workshop materials (e.g. had to copy the takeaways from a picture of sticky notes).
- Not all moderators and notetakers signed into the doc or Miro board. This made it difficult to track down the right person to get additional context from concerning the takeaways.
- Some groups took notes but did not write takeaways.
- Takeaways contributed via a Google doc more often had subpoints than those contributed via a Google slide.
- Each discussion session was asked to agree on 1-2 or 3-5 takeaways depending on the session slot length. Not all breakout sessions contributed takeaways, but the number of breakout sessions contributing at least one takeaway increased as the workshop progressed.
- **Lesson learned:** Google slides are easier to collect takeaways from discussions, provide a better template for contribution, and informally enforce the expectation to provide at least one takeaway from each discussion. Requires a little more setup than a notes doc, but the live navigation and contribution is much easier.
- **Lesson Learned:** Use the same structure in an early plenary session to introduce the format to the attendees for improved completeness for takeaway contributions from the breakout sessions. Could be a short 'practice' session with a single (and potentially narrow) topic.
- **Lesson Learned:** In addition to the above suggestion, it would be useful to have a pre-workshop tech orientation particularly geared towards virtual attendees to improve their comfort and ability to navigate the needed technologies for interaction.
- **Lesson Learned:** Might get more complete takeaway contributions if the importance is made clear early. Can discuss the three leading roles of each breakout session - moderator, notetaker, and reporter - where the reporter will present the agreed upon takeaways from the breakout session to the wider workshop audience. Often, the moderator will serve as the reporter.
- **Lesson Learned:** Creating a template for takeaways before the workshop would improve the input into the workshop report, but the template should be kept simple. E.g.:

- Day number, breakout session number, moderator name, notetaker name, reporter name
- Takeaway text
- Impact rating, effort rating, requires further discussion, requires community input, etc?
- Potential specific implementations?
- Hybrid interaction methods
 - Used the IO tool for questions in the plenary sessions to equalize the importance of questions from those in the room and those online. The questions were exported after each plenary session into a section in the plenary notes document for presenters to answer asynchronously.
 - Presenters and attendees (both virtual and in-person) indicated interest in answering and getting answers to the questions in a given plenary session, but were unable to due to the restrictions of the tools used.
 - **Lesson learned:** If possible, choose the settings on the tool used for Q&A to allow presenters to answer questions after the session is over. If not possible (e.g. need to reset the Q&A tool for the next session), export the unanswered questions into a persistent chat capability to support this interaction. Or use a different tool for Q&A that allows attendees to submit and vote on questions (e.g. a separate and persistent Padlet instance for each plenary session instead of the IO tool). Make sure to prepare these ahead of time and link to the workshop agenda.
 - Plenary moderators were careful to alternate between questions from those in the room and questions from those online.
 - Used two padlets to allow attendees, both in-person and remote, to suggest discussion ideas and then vote on them (padlet 1) and to vote on paths forward topics (padlet 2). Chose to use the 5-star rating method instead of a thumbs-up approach to allow more expression from the attendees in their votes.
 - **Lesson learned:** When analyzing reactions exported from padlet, make sure to consider both the average rating column and the number of ratings column. Items rated highly by only 2-3 people are not as important as items rated slightly less highly by a large number of people.
 - **Lesson learned:** Will likely get more thoughtful votes if the number of votes per person is limited (e.g. to 5ish). Can incorporate into the voting method if possible in the chosen technology or go with the honor system and acknowledge that some will use more.
 - **Lesson learned:** Add other members of the EC as moderators/editors to the padlets, IO tools, and similar to avoid single-point failures (e.g. if someone gets sick during the workshop).
 - Used a Miro board for each breakout discussion session on day 2. Some Miro boards were filled with ideas and comments, while others had only a few items. Some in-person sessions used sticky notes as a physical alternative. The session moderators of those sessions took pictures of those sticky notes with their phones and uploaded them into the workshop materials for preservation.

- The permissions on all Miro boards were set so that anyone could edit them, but with a password only communicated to attendees via email. This was to avoid inappropriate content from being added to those materials.
- Creating the Miro boards ahead of time allowed the permissions to be set in a protective but collaborative manner (anyone can edit but must have the password) and the same Miro board template to be used across the discussion sessions. This also avoided added cost by avoiding adding team members to the Miro board account. Moderators were trained ahead of time on how to copy their discussion topic title and description into their Miro board so that the action could be completed in a short amount of time at the beginning of their sessions.
- Discussion sessions were not hybrid with the rare exception of the 7150 session on day 2. This created more equal opportunities for those in-person and those online to contribute to the discussions. For each in-person discussion session on a given topic, there was a virtual discussion session on the exact same topic.
- All report back sessions were hybrid, with in-person and virtual moderators giving a 60-90 second report on the main takeaways of the discussion. This encouraged cross-communication of ideas between in-person and virtual attendees without creating more difficulty in attempting to have hybrid conversations.
- Virtual attendees were noted to make fewer comments and other verbal contributions during the hybrid sessions than those that attended in person.
- **Lesson learned:** The decision to separate the discussion sessions into virtual and in-person copies of the same materials went well. It was important to keep the report back sessions where the takeaways were presented hybrid to share those ideas across all attendees, both in-person and virtual.
- In-person and virtual attendees had difficulty communicating with each other during the workshop since the WebEx chat reset itself every time the attendee went to a different session.
- Virtual attendees had difficulty coordinating technical assistance since the WebEx chat reset itself every time the attendee went to a different session, including breakout sessions.
- **Lesson learned:** Use a separate persistent chat for the duration of the workshop, such as Slack, Discord, or Discourse to support attendees' need for communication during the workshop. Use this same chat for coordinating technical issues. Could have different threads on a Slack channel to support different purposes (e.g. technical, meet-ups, collaboration, posters).
- **Lesson learned: Never** schedule a NASA workshop in the first half of the month to avoid issues resulting from contract renewal problems. This created single-point failures, resulting in major technical issues with the hybrid lightning breakouts.
- Connecting the materials
 - The IO tool, main padlet, google drive folder, and workshop website links were all included at the top of the workshop agenda.
 - A slide deck was used to communicate room assignments and topic assignments and descriptions for the lightning and discussion breakout sessions. For the

discussion breakouts on Day 1, the links to the Miro boards were included on each slide of the room assignments slide deck.

- If a Miro board was prepared for a discussion session, it was linked from the Google doc where the notes were formatted for contribution ahead of time.
- **Lesson learned:** Linking everything from the notes document for each discussion breakout session was too labor intensive. Consider avoiding a notes document entirely and simply linking the Miro board to the topic title and description on the room assignments slide deck instead. The moderator can instruct attendees to put their names on the Miro board in a designated section during a short 'intro to Miro' tutorial at the beginning of the session. Takeaways can be copied into the slide for that specific discussion breakout session. This makes for better report back presentations of those takeaways too.
- **Lesson learned:** Add all the links for a given session to the workshop agenda to minimize how many clicks it takes for attendees to pull up the needed materials. Make sure to label the links clearly on the agenda to discriminate between resources for breakout sessions.

Feedback from the PC and EC members

- Miro boards worked really well in the virtual session. It made the Google document for the notes superfluous.
- **Lesson learned:** Have the moderators of the breakout session participate in a dry run amongst themselves. Then they can see how it's done, how the technology can be used, how to achieve group consensus on takeaways in the time allotted, and how to encourage collaboration during discussions. The purpose of such a dry run is so all the moderators can be on the same page for expectations. More in depth materials on this skill is available at <https://www.scrum.org/resources/getting-started-scrum-master>.
- At the beginning of the meeting, there were voiced concerns about the number of different tools used. That said, the organizers did a good job of using the right tool for the right job. Once attendees understood that and had a mental model of the tools, I believe they felt less overwhelmed.
- **Lesson learned:** Have a slide at the beginning of day one or at the top of the google doc explaining what the different tools are and when the tools will be used. Maybe a simple diagram explaining the "tools in our toolbox". Referencing the training materials available in the workshop information folder on the first day was not enough.
- Personally, I find that note taking can help in determining the takeaways (as moderator I would refer to the notes to ensure that the major discussion points were considered in formulating the takeaways). Notes can also provide additional context for interpreting the takeaways by others in cases where the brevity of a takeaway may lead to ambiguity or misinterpretation.
- We could have used 5 minutes (likely more) of transition time between the main room sessions and the breakouts to allow for getting to the breakout room, getting the technology set up, etc.

- **Lesson learned:** Allow at least 15 minutes of transition time between sessions to allow for those in-person to find the right room and those online to navigate to the correct meeting link. This also allows more time for minor technical issues to be resolved without cutting into that session's time allotment.
- Attendees in person lacked power resources for laptops in the middle of the room.
- **Lesson learned:** Run wires and power strips to each table.